

Awareness and Appreciation of Local Cultural Heritage of Surigao City

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ABSTRACT: As societies become increasingly interconnected, there is a growing need to recognize and celebrate the unique identities embedded in local traditions, customs, and artifacts. This study aimed to identify the level of awareness and appreciation of the local cultural heritage of the senior high school students of St. Paul University Surigao. This study applied the quantitative research design employing a descriptive survey technique with 272 participants. The main instrument employed in gathering the necessary data was the researcher-made questionnaire. The gathered data were treated using sample percentage, mean and standard deviation, and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC). The results showed that there is a significant relationship between students' awareness of local history and their appreciation for local cultural heritage in Surigao, and there is a positive correlation. The results of this research may provide fundamental information and a framework for future researchers doing thorough investigations that have similarities to this study.

KEYWORDS: Awareness and Appreciation of Local Cultural Heritage, Cultural Heritage, Local Cultural Heritage.

INTRODUCTION

Cultural heritage, as defined by NCCA (2018), refers to the totality of cultural property preserved and developed through time and passed on to posterity. There are categories highlighted as to natural heritage, intangible heritage, tangible movable heritage, and tangible immovable heritage, each of which has historical, scientific, aesthetic, and social significance.

Based on the cultural heritage categories set by NCCA, natural heritage covers natural geological and physiographical features, land formations, bodies of water, plants, and animals. Intangible heritage covers oral traditions and expressions, including language, performing arts, social practices, rituals and festive events, knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe, and traditional craftsmanship. Tangible movable heritage includes archaeological objects, ethnographic objects, religious objects, works of industrial and commercial arts, artwork, archival holdings, and natural history specimens. Tangible immovable heritage includes government structures, private-built structures, commercial establishments, schools and educational complexes, hospitals and health facilities, churches, temples, and places of worship; monuments and markers; sites; heritage houses; and vernacular architecture.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization makes it clear that cultural heritage is not limited to monuments and collections of objects but rather is "comprised of living expressions inherited from our ancestors, such as oral traditions, performing arts, social manners, rituals, festive events, knowledge and practices related to nature and the universe, and knowledge and techniques linked to traditional crafts" (UNESCO, 1972). The importance of cultural heritage for international relations is attributed to economic and social aspects. Despite having a long and rich culture, the preservation of cultural heritage in Indonesian cities is still facing numerous challenges. Modernization has gradually replaced countless historical monuments, and museums displaying the glory of previous civilizations are not as popular as other urban attractions. Different approaches should be considered to prevent further cultural loss and the fragmentation of Indonesian urban history. (Aritenang, 2022)

The Philippines, a nation rich in diverse traditions and complex history, faces a growing concern regarding the erosion of its cultural heritage amidst these modern shifts. (Alvero, 2023). The researchers identify issues like cultural appropriation, loss of indigenous knowledge, and the prioritization of economic development over heritage preservation, which add further urgency to the need for comprehensive research in this domain.

In an ever-changing global landscape, preserving cultural heritage is critical to ensuring the continuity of a country's identity, values, and traditions (Mekonnen, Bires, & Berhanu, 2022). Understanding the role and importance of cultural heritage begins in school, as education is a necessary and indispensable stage (Achille and Fiorillo, 2022).

The current problem faced by the Surigaonon people is their low understanding and awareness of history. At least humans must learn from their past or history. It is very necessary for everyone to understand history from an early age to know and understand the meaning of past events so that it can be used as a basis for attitudes in dealing with present realities and to determine the future. It means that history needs to be studied from an early age by every individual, either formally or non-formally, so that the relationship between individuals in a society or a nation forms an awareness of the importance of history on issues of common life such as nationalism, national unity, and integrity.

This study consists of an exploration of each home's culture as of today based on what is observed. The generation of today would prefer foreign influences on its own, so as a study, they would like to bring education and awareness to the youth of today to celebrate and not let the candle of their ancestors burn out and be forgotten but to be spread and celebrated.

At the present time, students in general appear not to be concerned all that much about cultural heritage. This might be because they are unaware of anything about it, they do not simply want to know, or they simply do not appreciate Surigao's culture. The researcher conducted this research to assist them in learning more about the local cultural heritage.

The researchers conducted this study not only because they are from the Arts and Design Track strand but also because they want to examine the relationship between high school students' awareness of the local history of Surigao City and their appreciation of Surigao City's local cultural heritage. Furthermore, the researchers noticed that only a few individuals truly value Surigao's cultural heritage and traditions. Researchers are more motivated in this circumstance to address the problem to inform and raise people's awareness. Recommendations will be provided after the outcomes have been identified.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored from Santos, L. (2021), discussing about the local historians and educators pursued its relevance to studying local history, particularly with Kasaysayang Lokal (KASALO) ng Pampanga. Based on her article, it is used to embark to the mind of today's learners the local history of their place. And the study was aimed to assess the local awareness of Junior High School students and its correlation to their appreciation of cultural heritage.

One of the reasons why generations of people document their history is because they want to ensure the stories told are accurately preserved. They want to make sure the knowledge of their culture is understood by the generations to come. There are a lot of experiences and an abundance of wisdom that can be lost as time passes if it's not recorded. When that information is documented, the reader, viewer, or listener has access to historical information that can be of significant value in the present time.

This study focused on knowing Awareness and Appreciation of Local Cultural Heritage under Arts and Design Track Strand of St. Paul University-Surigao and broke down its concern: the 'lack of knowledge with its own culture.' This was conducted during the school year of 2022-2023.

This study evaluated the utilization of awareness with local cultural history and how it affected the said participants. To better comprehend and recognize the distinction in this review, they are defined conceptually and operationally. Heritage is one of the conditions for the maintenance of a communicable memory and its effects. To preserve the heritage can also mean to preserve a set of connections to a given memory's 'furniture'. This one could be seen as a shared portion of experience which communicable potential relies in the heritage's materiality for effectiveness, somehow as people need a language to maintain a conversation. A preserved heritage would so be a maintained talk.

Consequently, the profiles of the respondents such as sex, strand, and gender level, also take account into consideration into their level of awareness and appreciation on Surigao's local cultural heritage.

Hence, the following profiles of the respondents are explained as follows:

Sex is the state of being male or female. that is assigned by a doctor at birth based on the genitals an individual is born with.

Strand are offerings in the Senior High School program of the Philippine's K-12 Basic Education Curriculum. It is intended for students who want to pursue higher education after they graduate from senior high. There are four Academic Track strands, namely Accountancy Business and Management (ABM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and the Science Technology

Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) strands. Furthermore, it includes the strand from the Technical-Vocational Livelihood and Arts and Design Track.

Grade level refers to all Senior High School students, the last two years of the K-12 program that DepEd has been implementing since 2012.

The framework of the study is illustrated in the schematic diagram in Figure I. There are four boxes. The first box shows the profile of the participants as to the sex, strand, and to their grade level.

One-line points to the second box, including the senior high school students' level of awareness of Surigao's cultural heritage. By being culturally aware, individuals can promote sustainability in the community and have a significant economic impact on the geography in which they are located due to the demand they generate for tourism. It also assesses the degree of knowledge that individuals have of their own community. Cultural assets must thus be acknowledged, valued, and protected by the society to which they belong. But when they have unconscious attitudes and behaviors regarding natural and cultural assets, it can lead to the destruction of cultural assets, especially in young people who will inherit the heritage.

Another line points to the third box, which contains the level of appreciation of Senior High School Students for Surigao's cultural heritage, in terms of appreciating each community's culture, which includes the senior high school students' level of appreciation for Surigao's cultural heritage. When appreciating the culture of a community, it needs to observe, learn, implementing, and adapting or realizing different customs and methods, which has led to a sense of unity among people. As individuals, each is free to experience whatever pleases them. This has definitely had a positive impact worldwide, and that needs to take immense pride in the rich and varied cultural heritage that gives people their very own individual identity.

On the fourth box, contains the proposal recommendations on what action should the senior high school students do in order to acknowledge the local cultural heritage of Surigao.

METHOD

This study applied the quantitative research design employing a descriptive survey technique with 272 participants. The respondents are the Senior High School students and the samples were selected using stratified random sampling. The main instrument employed in gathering the necessary data was the validated researcher-made questionnaire. The gathered data were treated using frequency count and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation, and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result and discussion of the data. The data presented follows the order of the problems cited in the statement of the problem; profile of the participants, awareness, and appreciation of the Senior High School students on Surigao

City’s local history, and the significant relationship between the level of awareness and appreciation of students on local history of Surigao as to profile.

Profile of the Participants

Table 1 presents the profile of the selected 272 Senior High School students as to sex, strand, awareness, and appreciation of local cultural heritage.

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

Profile	f (272)	%
Sex		
Male	110	40
Female	162	60
Strand		
STEM	142	52
ABM	43	16
HUMSS	66	24
ADT	5	2
TVL	16	6
Grade Level		
11	141	52
12	131	48

Table 1 presents the profile of the selected 272 Senior High School students as to sex, strand, awareness, and appreciation of local cultural heritage.

As to sex, mostly are females with 162 (60%), then males with 110 (40%). With regards to their strand, most of them belong in STEM or Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics strand with 142 (52%); then HUMSS or Humanities and Social Sciences strand with 66 (24%); ABM or Accountancy, Business, and Management strand with 43 (16%); TVL/ADT or Technical-Vocational-Livelihood strand with 16 (6%); and Arts and Design Track strand with 5 (2%).

Table 2. The Level of Awareness of Students on Local Cultural Heritage of Surigao

Indicators	M	SD	VI	QD
1. I can fluently speak and understand the local language(s) of Surigao City.	3.54	0.65	SA	FA
2. I attend local cultural events, festivals, or celebrations of cultural traditions of Surigao City.	3.12	0.75	A	A
3. I have knowledge of local history, folklore, customs, and traditions.	3.07	0.76	A	A
4. I observe and respect the traditional customs and rituals.	3.57	0.64	SA	FA
5. I adhere to the traditional clothing or attire that can be an outward expression of cultural awareness.	3.37	0.62	SA	FA
6. I enjoy eating and am familiar with the local cuisine.	3.48	0.64	SA	FA
7. I am interested in and support local art, music, dance, and other cultural expressions.	3.43	0.66	SA	FA
8. I am aware of the local social norms, manners, and etiquettes.	3.42	0.63	SA	FA
9. I support in preserving and promoting local museums, historical sites, and cultural institutions.	3.48	0.62	SA	FA
10. I participate in cultural education programs and workshops to learn more about the local culture.	3.17	0.75	A	A
Average	3.36	0.67	SA	FA

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Aware	FA
3	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Aware	A
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Somewhat Aware	SA
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Aware	NA

Table 2 displays the level of awareness of the Senior High School students on local history of Surigao. On average, it is verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Fully Aware* ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 0.67$). This implies that the students highly acknowledge and give respect to the history of Surigao up to the present time. They are still giving life to the history that all of their ancestors left for Surigao. As stated by Srivastava (2015), the success of heritage conservation initiatives depends on the understanding and participation of the local community.

As previously defined by Maria (2023), cultural awareness involves raising people's understanding of the influence their culture has on how they do things, including how they communicate, what foods they eat, or even how they go about their work. Being culturally aware means understanding why cultural diversity is important and recognizing that not every person will do things in the same manner as they do. Being mindful of this diversity allows them to be more respectful of the way others operate based on their cultural backgrounds. While individuals may not be intimately familiar with other cultures, if they at least understand their own culture and how it affects them, they can take the first step in developing a sense of cultural awareness when it comes to interacting with people who may have a different background than themselves.

Among the ten indicators, the item *I observe and respect the traditional customs and rituals* got the highest mean ($M=3.57$, $SD=0.64$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Fully Aware*. This means that the students do contribute a sense of comfort and belonging that brings a community together. For them, tradition reinforces values such as freedom, faith, integrity, a good education, and personal responsibility. But if they fail to fully understand the cultural heritage of Surigao City, as stated in an article from Importance of Cultural Awareness (n.d.), a lack of cultural awareness may lead people to misjudge people from other cultures. However, a lack of cultural awareness may lead to innumerable problems in communicating and understanding the intentions of others. Hence, cultural awareness helps individuals communicate and build strong relationships with others. Being culturally aware allows them to acknowledge their worldviews and heritage. They get a better understanding of the differences in the customs and beliefs of others. Exploring and educating themselves about different cultures helps them strengthen themselves. Eventually, they will discover that self-awareness and cultural awareness are really tied up with each other.

According to Forgeard (2023), he said that traditional values are beliefs, customs, and traditions that a society passes down from one generation to the next. These deeply rooted principles often stem from religious teachings, cultural norms, and shared experiences. They shape individuals' perceptions and behaviors toward family, community, and the world. The importance of traditional values lies in their role in maintaining social cohesion and stability. They provide a sense of continuity and collective identity and serve as a moral guide for individuals.

Evolve Communities (2023) asserts that culture not only influences social interactions but also defines a person's sense of self. They may improve their sense of self and form meaningful connections with individuals from all over the world by being culturally aware. Through cultural awareness, they can relate with others without discrimination or condemnation by acknowledging and appreciating their beliefs, customs, and values. As a result, there are more interactions between cultures and less disagreements between people brought on by cultural differences. Also, maintaining smaller and more isolated cultures is made possible by cultural understanding.

On the other hand, the item *I have knowledge of local history, folklore, customs, and traditions* got the lowest mean ($M=3.07$, $SD=0.76$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Agree* and qualitatively described as *Aware*. This indicates that students have the passion to know more the community's culture and its history. That they have interests or demonstrate the willingness to be conscious of the local cultural heritage.

This linked to Cassar (2021) study, it says that ignorance destroys heritage all the time. The cultural heritage is an asset of irreplaceable spiritual, cultural, social, and economic value, and its protection and promotion are indispensable for a balanced and complete life. The cultural heritage is an asset of irreplaceable spiritual, cultural, social, and economic value, and its protection and promotion are indispensable for a balanced and complete life (Languing et al., 2023)

Cultural ignorance can indeed lead to lost opportunities and increased levels of tension between people. When individuals or groups are not aware of or do not understand the customs, traditions, and beliefs of others, misunderstandings and conflicts can arise. This can hinder collaboration, communication, and mutual understanding, which are essential for personal and professional relationships to thrive (Gaddi, 2024). Embracing cultural awareness and empathy can help bridge gaps and foster respect and cooperation among diverse communities.

Table 3. The Level of Appreciation of Students on Local Cultural Heritage of Surigao

Indicators		M	SD	VI	QD
1.	I learned a lot regarding local history in high school.	3.28	0.70	SA	HA
2.	I have learned significant knowledge about Surigao City.	3.31	0.69	SA	HA
3.	I am interested in reading Surigaonon culture.	3.24	0.73	A	A
4.	I listened carefully while my teachers shared the local history and culture of Surigao.	3.33	0.69	SA	HA
5.	I explore literature written by local authors that provide me profound insights into the history, values, and perspective of a culture.	3.19	0.73	A	A
6.	I watch traditional performances that embody the essence of a culture.	3.32	0.76	SA	HA
7.	I purchase locally made crafts and products.	3.11	0.78	A	A
8.	I am mindful of cultural norms and customs by showing respect for local traditions.	3.42	0.68	SA	HA
9.	I explore museums and historical sites to understand the cultural and historical context of Surigao City.	3.10	0.82	A	A
10.	I appreciate the local environment and natural Landscapes of Surigao.	3.50	0.72	SA	HA
Average		3.28	0.73	SA	HA

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	SA	<i>Highly Appreciated</i>	HA
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Agree</i>	A	<i>Appreciated</i>	A
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Disagree</i>	D	<i>Somewhat Appreciated</i>	SA
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	SD	<i>Not Appreciated</i>	NA

Table 3 displays the the level of appreciation of students on local history of Surigao. On average, it is verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Appreciated* (M=3.28, SD=0.73). This shows that the students’ appreciation of studying local history gives a unique and powerful way to understand their place within their community. That they can develop stronger ties with their surroundings and the people who live there by piecing together the histories of their ancestors, family, friends, and neighbors that leads to a stronger sense of self and a better understanding of the present and the future.

Pindasu (2023), shared his statement in his research that people share cultural expressions that have been passed from one generation to another, have evolved in response to their environments, and contribute to giving us a sense of identity and continuity. Appreciating it makes individuals distinct and unique from our Southeast Asian neighbors but somehow related, especially from their ancient Austronesian roots, where they came from Southern China and migrated southward, where they already knew.

Local history matters because learning about history teaches essential skills (Gaddi, 2024). It pushes individuals to view the world from a different perspective. It teaches critical thinking when researching, like understanding biases and juggling multiple perspectives. This is especially relevant today, considering the availability of information online and the ever-growing need to examine reliability of information. Because a city is not a community without an understanding of its past. The traditions, stories and civic commemorations transform our city into a community. Telling these stories and continuing these local traditions help strengthen our community connection. (Poudre Landmarks, 2017)

Among the ten indicators, the item *I appreciate the local environment and natural Landscapes of Surigao* got the highest mean (M=3.50, SD=0.72), which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Appreciated*. This reveals that local environment and landscapes contribute to regional cultural identity and variety. Landscapes may be considered to be the product of human interactions with their surroundings. Communities must encourage their citizens' well-being. Creating entertainment venues is one method to address the requirements of both the mind and the body. And those interactions establish the foundation of community. (Keller R. et al., 2019) To put it simply, a cultural landscape is a historically significant property that shows evidence of human interaction with the physical environment. Cultural landscapes provide a sense of place and identity; they map humans’ relationship with the land over time; and they are part of people’s national heritage and each of our lives." These landscape categories help to distinguish the values that make them cultural resources and to determine how they should be treated, managed, and interpreted. (U.S. National Park Service, n.d.) As such, a cultural landscape is a place with many layers of history that evolves through design and use over time. A cultural landscape embodies the associations and uses that evoke a sense

of history for a specific place. Physical features of cultural landscapes can include trees, buildings, pathways, site furnishings, water bodies – basically any element that expresses cultural values and the history of a site. Cultural landscapes also include intangible elements such as land uses and associations of people that influenced the development of a landscape. Cultural landscapes include neighborhoods, parks and open spaces, farms and ranches, sacred places, etc. (*SF Planning*, 2023)

On the other hand, the item *I explore museums and historical sites to understand the cultural and historical context of Surigao City* got the lowest mean ($M=3.10$, $SD=0.82$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Agree* and qualitatively described as *Appreciated*. This means that historical sites not only serve as physical reminders of one’s ancestors’ achievements and contributions but also provide individuals with a deeper understanding of their past. They help people understand the way their ancestors lived, their values, beliefs, and cultural practices, and how they interacted with their environment. Historical sites not only serve as physical reminders of one’s ancestors’ achievements and contributions but also provide individuals with a deeper understanding of their past (Gaddi et al., 2024). They help everyone understand the way their ancestors lived, their values, beliefs, and cultural practices, and how they interacted with their environment. Historical sites also enable people to trace their ancestry, learn about their roots and develop a sense of connection and pride in one’s cultural identity. Protecting historical sites is also vital for future generations (Gaddi et al., 2024). These historical sites represent an invaluable resource that helps each learn about and understand their past, and they have the potential to inspire future generations. By protecting historical sites, they ensure that they remain available for future generations to learn from and appreciate. However, historical sites are often at risk of being destroyed or damaged due to natural disasters, urban development, neglect, or intentional destruction. Therefore, it is crucial that we take measures to protect them. This involves not only physical protection but also cultural preservation, education, and awareness-raising efforts. (Owens, J. 2023)

Different studies show that, heritage comes in many shapes—in tangible forms such as sites, buildings, landscapes, or as intangibles, like memories, emotions, values and customs—as does the use of heritage, ranging from the purpose of building nations to marketing places. (*Copernicus SEA*, n.d) *UNESCO* (2021) defines cultural heritage broadly as “the legacy of physical artefacts and intangible attributes of a group or society that are inherited from past generations, maintained in the present and bestowed for the benefit of future generations”. Cultural heritage cannot only be considered as an economic asset and a tourist attraction, but also as an identity factor and a contributor to social cohesion and stability.

Table 4. Significant Relationship between the Level of Awareness and Appreciation of Students on Local History of Surigao

IV	DV	r (x,y)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Awareness	Appreciation	0.593	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

P-value < 0.05 = Reject Ho

Table 4. The correlation analysis showed a Pearson-r value of (0.593). This indicates that the students’ awareness of local history has a positive correlation with students’ appreciation of cultural heritage in Surigao. This result suggests that when the students’ awareness on the local history of Surigao increases, their appreciation for Surigaonon cultural heritage increases by (0.593). The correlation results indicate that the students have a better appreciation for cultural heritage and do have a correspondingly better appreciation for their awareness level in history.

Meanwhile, the correlation’s p-value is (0.000), which indicates that the positive correlation found in the Pearson-r statistic is significant for this study. The study’s correlation analysis result is interesting in that it explained that there was a significant relationship between students’ awareness of local history and their appreciation for local cultural heritage in Surigao and has a positive correlation. The relationship items are culture-based initiatives that foster a respect for the historical and cultural significance of the area. There are things that humans regard as important to preserve for future generations. They may be significant due to their present or possible economic value, but also because they create a certain emotion within them or because they make each person feel as though they belong to something like a country, a tradition, or a way of life. They might be objects that can be held and buildings that can be explored, or songs that can be sung and stories that can be told. Whatever shape they take, these things form part of a heritage, and this heritage requires active effort on everyone’s part in order to safeguard it. (*UNESCO*, 2021).

Efforts like paying attention to it, recognizing it, and looking for it can serve to promote the local identity, regional languages, and minority cultures. Efforts can focus on preservation or promotion of a culture but can also use culture to mobilize the local population. Examples of cultural preservation or efforts focusing solely on a culture are often seen in relation to tourism and conservation efforts (Gaddi et al., 2024). The relationship between culture and community development is vast. However, this important relationship is rarely accorded a significant role in the design of development efforts. Using an interactional approach to community development provides opportunities for incorporating insights into the role and place of culture. Further, it means conceptualizing development to highlight the importance of establishing and enhancing social relationships. Aligning such development with cultural promotion and preservation can serve as a tool for successful development (Serato et al., 2024, Biyoyo et al., 2024).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study's objectives and findings, it is concluded that the senior high school students at St. Paul University Surigao showed that until now they had a positively high level of awareness of their Surigaonon local cultural heritage. Hence, senior high school students have shown a high appreciation for Surigao's local cultural heritage.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are based on the conclusion of the study:

1. For Senior High School Students of St. Paul University Surigao, they should continue to maintain their promotion of local heritage by informing about and preserving historical sites and artifacts, communicating with others about their experiences in the region, and sharing and celebrating customs and traditions, among others. Through these actions, others can appreciate and learn about their local heritage. Gaining an understanding of one's own culture and history may be extremely useful for retaining a nation's unique identity, fostering personal development, and promoting unity in society. It creates a more open and educated society and assists students in establishing links between their past and present while looking toward the future.
2. Cultural Heritage Center, the study recommends that schools may provide more novel ways to teach local history. More creative ways are needed for students to connect with their local histories and understand their community role. This can be accomplished by using innovative teaching methods or technology. Individuals can learn local history better when they are immersed in important historical or cultural sites. Educational tours need not be far, and the local community is rich with these exposure sites.
3. Teachers, educators may foster a deeper and more meaningful engagement between students and historical events and individuals by including experiential learning activities like debates, simulations, and historical reenactments. This can also serve as a guide for them to learn more about their own cultural heritage. With today's educational resources, students can enhance their learning experience by learning how to contribute to, preserve, and protect the significance of our past.
4. Surigao City Historian, ought to have an established foundation from which to promote the preservation and appreciation of the city's wealthy cultural heritage. This study may support academic research and be an essential tool for promoting community pride and a long-term cultural preservation effort.
5. For future researchers, due to the fact that only senior high school students were surveyed for this study, the objective is to educate students about cultural heritage for their future reference. All senior high school students have participated in surveys. In future studies, the researchers hope to offer the opportunity for other levels of education to get involved.

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